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To introduce primary school students to the objectives of mathematics

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Аннотация: В этой научной статье подробно объясняется, чему учит математика, каковы цели этого предмета и как объяснить важные аспекты этого предмета учащимся начальной школы

Ключевые слова: математика, объект, метод, метод наблюдения, национальная учебная программа.

Abstract: In this scientific article, it is fully explained what mathematics teaches, what are the goals of this subject, and how to explain the important aspects of this subject to elementary school students.

Key words: mathematics, object, method, observation method, national curriculum.

Annotatsiya: Ushbu ilmiy maqolada matematika fani nimani o'rgatadi, bu fanning maqsad vazifalari nimalardan iborat va boshlang'ich sinf o'quvchilariga ushbu fanning ahamiyatili tomonlarini tushuntirish haqida to'liq yoritib berilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: matematika, obyekt, metod, kuzatish metodi, milliy o'quv dastur.

The formation of the methodology of teaching mathematics in primary classes as a science. What should modern primary education consist of? What

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knowledge should a child have in grades 1-4? From when, how, and in what manner should we teach our children our national values, customs and traditions?" These questions are the main issue of primary education. In recent years, teaching mathematics in high school in our country, especially in the primary education system, has made and continues to make extremely large changes in terms of its scope and importance. Especially, the independence of our republic, the issuance of Laws and decrees on schools are a clear proof of this. The subject matter (object) of mathematics consists of spatial forms and quantitative relationships between them. The purpose of the school mathematics course is to form a system of mathematical knowledge for students taking into account their psychological characteristics. This system of mathematical knowledge is conveyed to students through certain methods (methodology). "Methodology" is a Greek word, and "method" means "way". Mathematical methodology is a branch of pedagogic science that is included in the system of pedagogic sciences, and in accordance with the educational goals set by the society, it applies the laws of teaching mathematics at a certain stage of the development of mathematics. Setting modern students and educational goals in front of the school led to a radical change in the content of mathematics education.

In order to provide effective mathematics education to elementary school students, it is necessary for the teacher to master the teaching methods for elementary grades consists of: 1 justification of the intended goals of teaching

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mathematics (Why is mathematics taught, taught?). 2. The scientific development of the content of mathematics education (what to teach) is how the level of knowledge presented in one system is distributed in accordance with the age characteristics of students, consistency is ensured in learning the basics of science, educational activities for educational work the educational load is solved, the content of education corresponds to the real knowledge capabilities of students. 3. Scientific development of teaching methods (how to teach, that is, what is the methodology of educational work so that students acquire the economic knowledge, skills, abilities, and mental activity that are needed today should be? 4. Development of teaching tools - textbooks, didactic materials, instructions, manuals and technical tools (with what to teach). 5. Scientific development of educational organization. (how to organize the lesson and extracurricular forms of education) The goals, content, methods, tools and forms of teaching are a complex system in the main components of the methodical system, which can be illustrated with a unique graph. Methodology of teaching mathematics other subjects, first of all, mathematics is inextricably linked with its basic subject. Modern mathematics relies on set theory to support the concept of natural numbers. In the first pages of modern elementary mathematics textbooks, we we come across assignments for students: "Paint as many squares in one row as there are rabbits in the picture, and as many squares as wolves in the 2nd row". Completing such tasks encourages children to establish mutual value correspondence between the elements of the

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indicated sets, which is important for the formation of the concept of natural numbers.

The general methodology depends on the level of education. The rules established by the general mathematics methodology are used by the primary mathematics teaching methodology, taking into account the age characteristics of young students. Primary school MOM is inextricably linked with pedagogy and pedagogical technology, ICT science, and relies on its laws. There is a two-way connection between MOM and pedagogy. On the one hand, the methodology of mathematics relies on the general theory of pedagogy and is formed on this basis, which ensures the unity of methodological and theoretical approaches in solving the problems of teaching mathematics. On the other hand, pedagogy relies on the result achieved by special methods in the formation of general laws, which ensures its viability and concreteness. Thus, pedagogy is "fed" from the concrete material of methodologies, it is used in pedagogical generalization and, in turn, serves as a guide for the development of methodologies. Mathematics teaching methodology is related to pedagogy, psychology and youth psychology. The theory and methodology of the primary mathematics course is related to other methods of education (methodology of mother tongue, science, art and other subjects). In order to properly implement integrated education in primary education, it is very important for the teacher to take this into account. Scientific research methods are methods of obtaining scientific information for the purpose of establishing legal

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connections, relationships, and creating scientific theories.

Scientific-pedagogical research methods include observation, experiment, familiarization with school documents, study of students' work, interviews and questionnaires. Recently, the use of mathematical and cybernetic methods, as well as teaching modeling methods, has been noted. (It is assumed that the student's thoughts can be drawn on the board and that the student can read the thoughts in the drawing). The methodology of teaching mathematics answers the following three questions related to the educational process:

1. Why should you study mathematics?
2. What should be learned from mathematics?
3. How to learn mathematics?

The concept of the methodology of mathematics was first described in the work of the Swiss pedagogue mathematician G. Pestalozzi in 1803 "Demonstrative study of number", the great thinker of elementary education Abu Rayhan Beruni, Abu Ali Ibn Sina and others In their views on education and upbringing, they put forward advanced ideas about the problems of learning the basics of primary education. divided into: 1. The general methodology of teaching mathematics. In this section, the goal, content, form, methods and tools of mathematics are disclosed based on pedagogy, psychological laws and didactic principles. 2. Special methodology of teaching mathematics. This section shows the ways of applying the laws and rules of the general methodology of teaching mathematics to

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specific topic materials. 3. Concrete methodology of teaching mathematics. This section consists of two parts: 1. Specific issues of the general methodology. 2. Specific issues of the special methodology. used by itself. The method of observation consists in perceiving the pedagogical process in a direct goal-oriented manner with appropriate recording of the results of observation under normal conditions. Monitoring will continue in the short and long term based on a plan with a specific goal in mind. Observation can be continuous or selective. The connection is more extensive in observation observed phenomena (for example, cognitive activities of young students in mathematics lessons), small-scale phenomena (for example, independent work of students in mathematics lessons) are observed during selective observation. An experiment is also an observation, conducted in a specially organized, controlled and systematically modified environment by the researcher. Analysis of the results of the experiment is carried out by the method of comparison. The interview method is also used in pedagogical research. Clearly identifying the goals and tasks of the research, developing its theoretical foundations and principles, creating a working hypothesis, are the main criteria in the formation of the methodology of teaching mathematics in elementary grades. Tasks of methodical-mathematical training of primary school teachers in our country in the era of rapid development of information and communication technologies, globalization, competition in the world market is becoming more and more intense, it is the most important value

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and decisive force in achieving the goals set in terms of democratic development, modernization and renewal. Education of an educated and intellectually developed generation is becoming an important factor. Expressing his opinion that in the "Strategy of Actions on Five Priority Areas of Development of the Republic of Uzbekistan in 2017-2021" specific mechanisms for raising the standard of living of our people have been determined, he drew the attention of this strategy not only to our people, but also to the world community. We would like to emphasize that it has become an important document that attracts people. As a result of the rapid development of the society, the information environment and the situation in the labor market, the reproductive education system did not meet the requirements of the time. This requires the development of new approaches to teaching mathematics. In order to deepen the knowledge and talent of young people, to ensure their participation in the further development of Uzbekistan as qualified personnel in the future, modern approaches are being introduced to the educational process. The prosperity and stable development of our country depends to a certain extent on deep knowledge, strong faith and, in general, being a perfect human being. There is a demand for people who can actively solve the problems that arise in front of our society, who understand the conditions well, who think comprehensively, who can understand, analyze, compare, and solve practical problems of daily and professional life. As we all know, the science of mathematics develops a person's mind, develops his attention, educates

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determination and will to achieve the intended (developed) goal, ensures algorithmic discipline in him, and most importantly his thinking expands. So, a modern person should be able to make independent decisions, work in a team, take initiative, adapt to new things, be resistant to stressful and nervous situations, and be able to get out of these situations. All such qualities can be achieved on the basis of using the competence approach in mathematics education. Today, in economically developed countries, the competency-based approach has modernized the content of education and become one of the new directions of teaching. The basis of the new content of general education in these countries is the formation and development of basic competencies of students. Competency approach to education, as opposed to the outdated concept of "acquisition of knowledge, skills and competence", refers to the acquisition by students of various forms of competences that allow them to act effectively in situations encountered in professional, personal and everyday life in society holds.

Thus, in the competency-based approach, the basis of mathematical education is focused on strengthening the practical, applied directions. In addition, the educational standards that are being created should reflect the qualities that are necessary for students to study in higher education institutions, to become holders of various professions and to be active citizens in all respects. The integration of our country into the world community, the development of science and technology, and the competitiveness of the young generation in the changing world require

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perfect mastery of the sciences, which is achieved by introducing international standards for teaching mathematics into the educational system of the Republic of Uzbekistan is mounted.

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